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Research Article

**RP- HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR
SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF GLECAPREVIR AND
PIBRENTASVIR IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM****Dr.Gampa VijayKumar^{1,2}, D. Sumanth Reddy³**

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Abstract

High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tool of the analysis. The estimation of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was p^H 4.5 and the mobile phase was optimized with consists of Methanol: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of P^H 4.5(20:80 v/v). kromosil C_{18} Column (250mm x 4.6mm) 5 μ g or equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 254 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . the linearity range of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir were found to be from 100-500 μ g/ml of Glecaprevir and 1-5 μ g/ml of Pibrentasvir. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999. The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. Glecaprevir %RSD 0.2 and Pibrentasvir %RSD 0.6. Intermediate precision for Glecaprevir %RSD 0.2 and Pibrentasvir %RSD 0.1 The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit. The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements. It inferred the method found to be simple, accurate, precise and linear. The method was found to be having suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

Keywords: kromosil C_{18} , Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir, RP-HPLC

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INTRODUCTION:**1.1 Analytical chemistry**

Analytical chemistry is a scientific discipline used to study the chemical composition, structure and behaviour of matter. The purposes of chemical analysis are together and interpret chemical information that will be of value to society in a wide range of contexts. Quality control in manufacturing industries, the monitoring of clinical and environmental samples, the assaying of geological specimens, and the support of fundamental and applied research are the principal applications. Analytical chemistry involves the application of a range of techniques and methodologies to obtain and assess qualitative, quantitative and structural information on the nature of matter.

- ❖ **Qualitative analysis** is the identification of elements, species and/or compounds present in sample.
- ❖ **Quantitative analysis** is the determination of the absolute or relative amounts of elements, species or compounds present in sample.

Structural analysis is the determination of the spatial arrangement of atoms in an element or molecule or the identification of characteristic groups of atoms (functional groups). An element, species or compound that is the subject of analysis is known as analyte. The remainder of the material or sample of which the analyte (s) form (s) a part is known as the matrix.

The gathering and interpretation of qualitative, quantitative and structural information is essential to many aspects of human endeavour, both terrestrial and extra-terrestrials. The maintenance of an improvement in the quality of life throughout the world and the management of resources heavily on the information provided by chemical analysis. Manufacturing industries use analytical data to monitor the quality of raw materials, intermediates and finished products. Progress and research in many areas is dependent on establishing the chemical composition of man-made or natural materials, and the monitoring of toxic substances in the environment is of ever increasing importance. Studies of biological and other complex systems are supported by the collection of large amounts of analytical data. Analytical data are required in a wide range of disciplines and situations that include not just chemistry and most other sciences, from biology to zoology, butte arts, such as painting and sculpture, and archaeology. Space exploration and clinical diagnosis are two quite desperate areas in which analytical data is vital. Important areas of application include the following.

1.2 Chromatography**1.2.1 Introduction**

The chromatography was discovered by Russian Chemist and botanist Micheal Tswett (1872-1919) who first used the term chromatography (colour writing derived from Greek for colour – Chroma, and write – graphein) to describe his work on the separation of coloured plant pigments into bands on a column of chalk and other material such as polysaccharides, sucrose and insulin.

“Chromatography is a method in which the components of a mixture are separated on an adsorbent column in a flowing system”.

The adsorbent material, or stationary phase, first described by Russian scientist named Tswett in 1906, has taken many forms over the years, including paper, thin layers of solids attached to glass plates, immobilized liquids, gels, and solid particles packed in columns. The flowing component of the system, or mobile phase, is either a liquid or a gas. Concurrent with development of the different adsorbent materials has been the development of methods more specific to particular classes of analytes. In general, however, the trend in development of chromatography has been toward faster, more efficient. “In his early papers of Tswett (1906) stated that chromatography is a method in which the component of a mixture are separated on an adsorbent column in a flowing system. Chromatography has progressed considerably from Tswett’s time and now includes a number of variations on the basic separation process”.

“Chromatography is a physical method of separation in which the component to be separated are distributed between two phases of which in stationary while other moves in a definite direction (IUPAC)”

MATERIALS AND METHOD AND INSTRUMENTATION:

HPLC Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20

Solution UV double beam UV3000 UV Win5 Lab India Digital weighing pH meter Ultrasonicator Suction pump.

Faxofenadine and Montelukast,

Potassium dihydrogen, Acetonitrile, Methanol, Water.

Water and Methanol for HPLC, Acetonitrile for HPLC, Ortho phosphoric Acid, KH_2PO_4

METHODOLOGY:**HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT****Mobile Phase Optimization:**

Initially the mobile phase tried was methanol: Ammonium acetate buffer and Methanol: phosphate buffer with various combinations of pH as well as varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was

optimized to potassium dihydrogen phosphate with buffer (pH 4.5), Methanol in proportion 20: 80 v/v respectively.

Wave length selection:

UV spectrum of 10 µg / ml Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir in diluents (mobile phase composition) was recorded by scanning in the range of 200nm to 400nm. From the UV spectrum wavelength selected as 254. At this wavelength both the drugs show good absorbance.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various columns like C18 column, hypersil column, lichrosorb, and inertsil ODS column. InertsilODS (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 0.8ml/min flow.

OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS:

Trial-6
Table 1.Chromatographic condition

Parameters	Description
Flow rate	1ml min ⁻¹
Column	kromosil C ₁₈ Column (250mm x 4.6mm)5µg.
Mobile Phase	Phosphate buffer:Methanol P ^H 4.5(20:80 v/v)
Buffer	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate PH 4.5 adjusted with Orthophosphoric acid
Detector	PDA
Column temperature	Ambient
Type of elution	Isocratic
Wavelength	254 nm
Injection volume	20µl
Run time	10min

Fig.no.1 Chromatogram of Trail-6

Observation: The separation of two analytical peaks was good. The plate count also above 2000, tailing factor below 2, and the resolution is above 2. The condition is taken as optimized method.

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

Tailing factor for the peaks due to Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir in Standard solution Should not be more than 2.0

Theoretical plates for the Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir peaks in Standard solution should not be less than 2000.

PRECISION

Accurately weigh and transfer 25 mg of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION/RUGGEDNESS:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method,

Precision was performed on different day by using different make column of same dimensions.

ACCURACY

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir 10mg of working standard into a 10mL & 100ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

LINEARITY

Accurately weigh 10 tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer equivalent to 10 mg of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir (marketed formulation) sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Glecaprevir working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Glecaprevir working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

ROBUSTNESS:

As part of the Robustness, deliberate change in the Flow rate, Mobile Phase composition, Temperature Variation was made to evaluate the impact on the method.

The flow rate was varied at 0.8 ml/min to 1.2ml/min. Standard solution 300ppm of Glecaprevir & 3ppm of Pibrentasvir was prepared and analysed using the varied flow rates along with method flow rate.

RESULTS:**SYSTEM SUITABILITY**

Table 2: Results of system suitability parameters for Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir

S.No	Name	Retention time(min)	Area (μ V sec)	Height (μ V)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Glecaprevir	3.855	1308495	154566	1.3	1.3	6090.3
2	Glecaprevir	3.902	1309496	156428	1.3	1.3	5023.2
3	Glecaprevir	3.903	1306498	152634	1.3	1.3	8060.7
4	Glecaprevir	3.904	1342499	158426	1.3	1.3	7080.1
5	Glecaprevir	3.905	1343451	158484	1.3	1.3	6054.4
6	Glecaprevir	3.906	1346455	158423	1.3	1.3	7080.6
7	Pibrentasvir	2.669	124505	223532	1.2	1.2	4523.3
8	Pibrentasvir	2.5264	123442	134544	1.2	1.2	5020.2
9	Pibrentasvir	2.5265	123431	124386	1.2	1.2	4061.2
10	Pibrentasvir	2.5266	125432	134568	1.2	1.2	5032.4
11	Pibrentasvir	2.5267	122434	146852	1.2	1.2	5076.4
12	Pibrentasvir	2.5268	124438	145782	1.2	1.2	6024.8

PRECISION:**Table.No.3. Showing %RSD results method precession for Glecaprevir**

Injection	Peak Name	Rt	Area	Height
1	Glecaprevir	3.699	123149	248742.3
2	Glecaprevir	3.790	123766	281441.2
3	Glecaprevir	3.663	124271	271721.2
4	Glecaprevir	3.658	124691	284393.8
5	Glecaprevir	3.647	124956	256318.0
6.	Glecaprevir	3.645	125845	226813.0
mean			124162.7	
Std.dev			725.6	
%RSD			0.6	

Table.No.4 Showing% RSD results method precession for Pibrentasvir

Injection	Peak Name	Rt	Area	Height
1	Pibrentasvir	3.616	1302729	341432.2
2	Pibrentasvir	3.634	1302947	523341.4
3	Pibrentasvir	3.460	1303236	374642.4
4	Pibrentasvir	3.446	1303977	327514.3
5	Pibrentasvir	3.437	1309759	374028.1
6	Pibrentasvir	3.438	1309789	346280.2
mean			1304529.8	
Std.dev			2961.1	
%RSD			0.2	

INTERMEDIATE PRECESSION (RUGGEDNESS):**Table.No 5 Showing results for intermediate precision of Glecaprevir**

INJECTION	Peak name	Rt	Area	Height
1	Glecaprevir	2.554	122487	438467.1
2	Glecaprevir	2.557	122626	436873.3
3	Glecaprevir	2.563	122632	438572.1
4	Glecaprevir	2.562	122702	435587.5
5	Glecaprevir	2.561	122962	432826.4
6	Glecaprevir	2.561	122972	432838.3
mean			122681.8	
Std.dev			174.8	
%RSD			0.1	

Table.No.6 Showing results for intermediate precision of Pibrentasvir

INJECTION	Peak name	Rt	Area	Height
1	Pibrentasvir	3.790	122487	241421.6
2	Pibrentasvir	3.657	122626	233417.3
3	Pibrentasvir	3.663	122632	281751.1
4	Pibrentasvir	3.646	122702	241843.6
5	Pibrentasvir	3.662	122962	281564.1
6	Pibrentasvir	3.663	122972	284917.2
mean			122681.8	
Std.dev			174.8	
%RSD			0.1	

ACCURACY:

Table7DetailsofAccuracy 50 %

INJECTION	Peak Name	RT	Area	Height
1	Glecaprevir	3.881	62252.5	21744
2	Glecaprevir	3.882	62253.4	21909
3	Glecaprevir	3.792	62148.5	21382
Mean			62218.13	
Std.Dev			60.30591	
% RSD			0.09692	

INJECTION	Peak Name	RT	Area	Height
1	Pibrentasvir	2.572	671725.5	86026
2	Pibrentasvir	2.573	671729.3	85549
3	Pibrentasvir	2.576	671638.5	84196
Mean			671697.8	
Std.Dev			51.36159	
% RSD			0.007647	

Table8DetailsofAccuracy 100 %

INJECTION	Peak Name	RT	Area	Height
1	Glecaprevir	3.546	124465	21784
2	Glecaprevir	3.542	122428	25909
3	Glecaprevir	3.546	124345	21372
Mean			123746	
Std.Dev			1142.997	
% RSD			0.923664	

INJECTION	Peak Name	RT	Area	Height
1	Pibrentasvir	2.306	132405	86096
2	Pibrentasvir	2.243	132452	86549
3	Pibrentasvir	2.223	133232	84176
Mean			132696.3	
Std.Dev			464.4958	
% RSD			0.350044	

Table9DetailsofAccuracy 150 %

INJECTION	Peak Name	RT	Area	Height
1	Glecaprevir	3.841	135545	21682
2	Glecaprevir	3.882	132558	25508
3	Glecaprevir	3.842	134345	21476
Mean			134149.3	
Std.Dev			1503.082	
% RSD			1.120455	

Table-10 accuracy (recovery) data for Glecaprevir

INJECTION	Peak Name	RT	Area	Height
1	Pibrentasvir	2.592	142526	76083
2	Pibrentasvir	2.573	142527	76348
3	Pibrentasvir	2.223	143532	74275
Mean			142861.7	
Std.Dev			580.5259	
% RSD			0.406355	

Table-11 accuracy (recovery) data for Pibrentasvir

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	62252.5	5.3	5.34	100.8%	100.51%
100%	124505	10	10.10	100.01%	
150%	186757.5	14.2	14.45	99.68%	

Table 12 accuracy (recovery) data for Pibrentasvir

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	671725.5	5.0	5.036	100.7%	99.84%
100%	1343451	10.0	10.003	100.0%	
150%	2015177	14.4	14.224	98.780%	

LINEARITY:

Figure 2 calibration graph for Glecaprevir at 254 nm

Figure 3 calibration graph for Pibrentasvir at 254 nm

Table-13 Area of different concentration of Glecaprevir

S.No.	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	100ppm	66510
2	II	200ppm	94701
3	III	300ppm	124802
4	IV	400ppm	152731
5	V	500ppm	179732
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Table-14 Area of different concentration of Pibrentasvir

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	1ppm	668934
2	II	2ppm	956781
3	III	3ppm	1313873
4	IV	4ppm	1563458
5	V	5ppm	1867084
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Table-15 Analytical performance parameters of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir???

Parameters	Glecaprevir	Pibrentasvir
Slope (m)	66574	12529
Intercept (c)	53592	50245
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.999	0.999

LOD**Table-16 Results of LOD**

Drug name	Baseline noise(μ V)	Signal obtained (μ V)	S/N ratio
Glecaprevir	52	152	2.9
Pibrentasvir	52	156	3

Table no-17 Results of LOQ

Drug name	Baseline noise(μ V)	Signal obtained (μ V)	S/N ratio
Glecaprevir	52	522	10.03
Pibrentasvir	52	524	10.1

ROBUSTNESS:**Variation In Flow****Figure no 4 chromatogram showing less flow of 0.6ml/min**

Figure no 5 chromatogram showing more flow of 1.0ml/min

Table-18 Flow Rate (ml/min) data for Glecaprevir

S.No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.6	5339.9	1.4
2	0.8	4673.4	1.3
3	1.0	5216.0	1.4

Table-19 flow rate (ml/min) data for Pibrentasvir

S.No	FlowRate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	7063.3	1.3
2	1.0	6090.3	1.2
3	1.2	6998.0	1.3

6.3.7.2 Variation Of Mobile Phase Organic Composition:

Figure no6 chromatogram showing less organic composition

Figure no 7 chromatogram showing more organic composition

Table -20 Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase for Glecaprevir

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	10% less	4508.4	1.3
2	*Actual	4673.4	1.4
3	10% more	4318.1	1.3

Table -21 Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase for Pibrentasvir

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	10% less	6387.7	1.2
2	*Actual	6090.3	1.2
3	10% more	6232.5	1.2

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tool of the analysis. The estimation of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate

buffer was p^H 4.5 and the mobile phase was optimized with consists of Methanol: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of P^H 4.5(20:80 v/v). kromosil C₁₈ Column (250mm x 4.6mm)5 μ gor

equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 254 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . The linearity range of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir were found to be from 100-500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Glecaprevir and 1-5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Pibrentasvir. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999. The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. Glecaprevir %RSD 0.2 and

Pibrentasvir %RSD 0.6. Intermediate precision for Glecaprevir % RSD 0.2 and Pibrentasvir %RSD 0.1. The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Glecaprevir and Pibrentasvir. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit. The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements. It inferred the method found to be simple, accurate, precise and linear. The method was found to be having suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS:

Parametres	Acceptance Criteria	Glecaprevir	Pibrentasvir
linearity	Correlation Coefficient 0.999	0.999	0.999
System precession	The Method precision study was performed for the %RSD	0.2	0.6
Intermediate precession	The intermediate precision was performed for %RSD	0.2	0.1
accuracy	% recovery was found to be (97-103%).	99.84(%)	100.51(%)
robustness	method is robust even by change in the flow rate $\pm 0.2\text{ ml/min}$	1.4	1.3
lod	-	2.9	3
loq	-	10.03	10.1

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